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CLASSIFICATION SYSTEM OF APPLIED PROGRAMS

Summary:

The article analyzes the applied programs in the software system. Attention was paid to the piece of software. A brief description of the software is given. The essence of applied software and their role in the educational process was widely revealed. The role of operating systems in the software system was also noted. At the same time, information about the software shell of operating systems is given. This article reflects information about utilities. Revealed their educational functions.

Key words: software, classification, application programs, operating system.

Their classification also has an important role in determining the psychological basis of applied programs. So, any classification is the result of logical thinking. In fact, mental processes are complexly involved in the classification of applied programs.

First of all, we need to consider the application programs as a system. Software (English software) is a set of programs that ensure the functional functioning of a computer to solve issues related to a number of disciplines. Software is an integral part of a computer system, a logical continuation of technical means, and defines the fields in which the computer is applied.

The software of modern computers includes quite a variety of programs. They can be conventionally divided into three groups.

- 1) System software (system programs),
- 2) application software (application programs),
- 3) instrumental provision (instrumental programs).

Application program assignment (TPT) is for the user to perform their own tasks. It includes: user application programs and multi-purpose application program package (TPP). A user application provides assistance in performing a task in any problem area. These programs can also be implemented as part of software packages and packages, as well as autonomously.

Application software package — this is a specially designed software package. It is generally applicable to any problem area and is complemented by appropriate technical documentation. There are following types of application package:

I. General purpose TPP. These are universal software products that automate a wide range of user tasks. They include:

1. Text editors (MS Word, Word Perfect),
2. Spreadsheet processors (MS Excel, Lotus 1-2-3, Quattro Pro),
3. System of dynamic presentations (MS Power Point, Freelance Graphics, Harvard Graphics),
4. Database management system (MS Access, Oracle, MS SQL Server, Informix),
5. Graphic editors (Corel Draw, Adobe Photoshop),
6. Publishing system (Page Maker, Venture Publisher),
7. Design automation system (BPWin, ERWin),

8. Electronic dictionaries and translation system (Prompt, Socrates, Linguo, Context),

9. Text recognition system (Fine Reader, Cunei Form).

General-purpose systems integrate office activities (Microsoft Office, Star Office, etc.) with office suites: multi-component packages that are often used to automate.

II. Method-oriented TPP. Solving problems by mathematical methods is the function of this package. For example, mathematical processing of data (Mathematica, MathCad, Maple) and statistical processing (Statistica, Stat) belong here.

III. Problem-oriented TPP. It is to perform certain tasks in any subject area through this package. For example, information-legal systems, accounting control packages, etc.

IV. Integrated TPP. Several software products collected on the basis of a single instrument are combined here. The most developed of them are: text editor, personal manager (organizer), spreadsheet, database management system, tools to support e-mail, creating software for creating presentation graphics. The results obtained by separate sub-programs can be combined into a final document such as tables, graphs and text material. For example, MS Works is their respective package. As a rule, integrated packages form a core, which creates interaction between the components that make it up.

Usually, the application package contains debugging tools. When using them, this tool is adapted to the specifics of any subject area.

Since it forms a single system with application programs, we feel it necessary to give brief information about system software (SPT). It is a program that manages work with the computer and performs various auxiliary functions. For example: manages computer resources, creates copies of information, checks the functionality of computer devices, provides information about the computer, etc. They are intended for users of all categories, ensure the effective functioning of the user and the computer. Most importantly, it helps in effective execution of application programs. The relationship between system software and applications is more important than the relationship between other tools.

Operating system occupies the central place among system programs. The operating system is a

program designed to manage downloads, launch other user programs, plan and manage EHM's computing resources, and manage all actions from EHM's connection to the electrical circuit to disconnection. As soon as the computer starts up, the program automatically connects, communicates with the user, manages the computer, its resources (operational memory, disk space, etc.), launches other programs for execution, and creates an efficient communication style between the user and the programs. This is done through the computer interface. In other words, the operating system creates a connection between all the components of the computer and ensures the functional functioning of these components, while at the same time making the hardware capabilities available for use.

Service systems are for servicing the operating system. It is designed for user convenience. Technical service system, operating system environment software overlays and service programs are included in the category of service systems. Preservation of information is one of the types of services provided by computers. Information is complete information about a certain subject and reality. For example, information about employees in each department of the enterprise (personnel record sheet) is stored. The data (elements) of this information are: name, surname, birth, nationality, which university and year he graduated, list of his scientific works, etc. With the help of information, a specific object, subject, event, environment, etc. knowledge is obtained. The collection of knowledge obtained through information is called information.

Let's assume that the observer collects information about the state of the studied object and stores it in memory in a certain form. Then they say that the observer's memory stores data reflecting the state of the object. Thus, data is information recorded in a certain form for storage, processing and transmission.

Data may sometimes express imprecise concepts that do not exist in reality. Data is a description of any event or idea that is important to us.

Traditionally, data is recorded in a specific medium (stone, tablet, paper) with specific means of communication (language or image). Over time, data representation methods and carriers have changed. Magnetic media (tape, disk, card), flexible optical disks, flash memory, etc. as a data carrier in a computer. is used. Data are mainly defined by data name, value, type, structure characteristics. The name of the data indicates its meaning. The price of data determines it itself.

The technical service system is a set of tools for the software-hardware system of a personal computer. They carry out control, testing and diagnostics, check the functionality of computer devices. Thus, it detects a malfunction in the computer during the work process. They act as a tool of specialists for technical repair of computer equipment.

The software overlay of operating systems is used to organize the user's interface with the computer in a more convenient and visual way. These are the programs that allow the user: to perform actions on the management of computer resources, unlike the

operating system tools presented to him (more clear and effective). Examples of these are Norton Commander (Symantec), FAR (File and Archive manager) (Е.Рошаль) packages.

Utility programs (utilities). These are auxiliary programs. They provide the user with frequently performed tasks or a number of additional services that increase the ease and comfort of the work. These programs include the following:

- software archivers. These allow information to be compacted onto disks. At the same time, it helps to save copies of several files in the form of an archive file;

- antivirus programs. It serves to protect the computer from viruses and eliminate the consequences of the virus. This is important for any computer user;

- disk space quality control and optimization programs;

- information restoration and optimization, data protection program;

- programs for writing CDs;

- drivers. They are programs that expand the capabilities of the operating system, such as managing input and output devices and RAM. When connecting new devices to the computer, you need to install the appropriate drivers;

- communication programs. Organizes information exchange between computers.

All the programs we have listed above, especially the service and maintenance programs, play an important role in the implementation of application programs. These programs make the user's work easier, more effective, and help him to easily solve any technical problem that he may encounter. The effective use of applied programs in the learning process cannot be imagined without connection with these programs.

Recently, the use of distance education and telecommunications systems has led to the emergence of the term "electronic textbook". In this regard, the resources of the Ministry of Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan are sufficient. Electronic textbooks for all classes and all subjects are available at <https://e-derlik.edu.az/site/index.php>.

Electronic textbooks are mostly in the form of hypertext. Here, information on each subject is collected in the form of a complex consisting of graphic, methodical and software tools. Such textbooks combine at least 6 components: information provision (hypertexts with graphic illustrations of educational materials); album of dynamic drawings; a training package for controlling control, simulation and other dialog programs; software (methodical instructions for conducting laboratory practice); system software for the integration of other components of the electronic textbook into a single system and to provide the service needed by the user. Searching for information in the electronic textbook is achieved on the basis of an interactive method.

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